

16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37

ABSTRACT

Through its atmospheric teleconnections, El Niño Southern Oscillation (ENSO) shifts and disrupts weather and climate patterns far beyond the equatorial Pacific where it occurs, and occasionally has catastrophic consequences in many countries of the world. It is also the largest source of seasonal and interannual climate predictability. Despite its huge importance, ENSO forecasting is still not performed operationally at longer leads than about 6 months ahead. At the same time, there is mounting scientific evidence that forecasts are possible even more than a year in advance. Early warning of ENSO could substantially mitigate and help avoid some of the most damaging impacts, such as floods, droughts, harvest failure, famine, migration and disease outbreaks. Here, we present forecasts from a statistical ENSO model of the next El Niño predicted to occur in the winter of 2023/24, at lead times between 11 and 17 months ahead of an expected peak in December 2023. We use a statistical unobserved dynamic components model (EDCM) based on subsurface ocean temperatures as well as sea surface temperatures and zonal wind stress. EDCM has been previously validated through hindcasts of the major El Niños since 1970, and through real time forecasts of the 2015/16 and 2018/19 El Niños. Our statistical method and results indicate that there is potential for doubling the operational predictive lead time of ENSO to at least 12 months, with additional promise for even earlier anticipation of 19 months. Such longer-lead forecasts could be of high value, because decision-making and management in a number of key socio-economic sectors could be greatly improved.

38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46

SIGNIFICANCE STATEMENT

We employ a statistical ENSO model and show early forecasting of the 2023 El Niño (EN). Early forecasts initiated in May and July 2022 predicted a mild EN. Forecasts initiated later, in November 2022 and January 2023, predicted a moderate EN, with a strong event falling within the 70% confidence intervals. This work confirms that statistical long-lead ENSO forecasts are feasible, and should be developed further in advance of the operational threshold of 6-8 months. Such forecasts are of high value for agriculture, water management, disaster reduction, public health and energy production in countries affected by ENSO. More so, a strong EN could lead to a

47 temporary breach of the 1.5°C threshold for global mean temperature increase set in
48 the Paris Climate Agreement.

49 CAPSULE (BAMS ONLY)

50 We predicted that El Niño will occur in the winter of 2023/24 at longer lead times (11-
51 17 months in advance) compared to the operational forecasts of 6-8 months ahead.

52 **1. Introduction**

53 El Niño Southern Oscillation (ENSO) and its predictability is a subject of widespread
54 scientific and societal interest, both because of its complexity as the dominant
55 atmosphere-ocean coupled mode of climate variability (Wyrтки, 1975, Philander
56 1983), and its links to multiple climate hazards worldwide (Sarachik and Cane, 2010).
57 A large number of ENSO prediction models have been described in the literature, and
58 the operational ENSO forecasting plume includes contributions from many statistical
59 and dynamical models (Barnston et al. 2012). Official forecasts are issued and
60 reported regularly by the International Research Institute for Climate and Society
61 Earth Institute (IRI, <https://iri.columbia.edu/our-expertise/climate/enso/>), and by the
62 National Atmospheric and Oceanic Administration and the Climate Prediction Center
63 (NOAA/CPC, https://www.cpc.ncep.noaa.gov/products/analysis_monitoring/enso_advisory/)
64 about two seasons in advance. However, ENSO forecasting is currently not
65 performed operationally at longer lead times (beyond 6 months in advance), despite
66 the growing number of studies indicating that a longer predictability range is feasible
67 (Cane et al. 1986; Goswami and Shukla 1991; Latif et al. 1998; Chen and Cane 2008;
68 Wittenberg et al. 2014; Gonzalez and Goddard 2016; Luo et al. 2016; DiNezio et al.
69 2017; Astudillo et al. 2017). Given that the ENSO forecasts are also the largest source
70 of seasonal precipitation and temperature predictability for the Pacific and North
71 Atlantic regions, North and South America, Australia, the Maritime Continent, and
72 parts of Asia and Africa (Ropelewski and Halpert 1987, Rodó et al. 2006, Sarachik
73 and Cane 2010, Kumar et al. 2017, L'Heureux et al. 2020), early anticipation through
74 long-lead forecasts could have huge economic, societal and health benefits that are
75 currently underutilized.

76 A handful of studies have already documented long-lead forecasts of past ENSO
77 events (Latif et al. 1998; Chen et al. 2004; Luo et al. 2008; Izumo et al. 2010;
78 Ludescher et al. 2013, 2014; Petrova et al. 2017; Gonzalez and Goddard 2016;

79 Ramesh et al. 2017; Luo et al. 2017; Meng et al. 2020, Petrova et al. 2020), with the
80 majority of these being based on dynamical models. In the 1980s and 1990s
81 substantial efforts were made to implement a monitoring system within the Tropical
82 Ocean Global Atmosphere (TOGA) Program, formed by a three-dimensional array
83 that regularly samples the surface and subsurface temperature, salinity and circulation
84 in the tropical Pacific, with the specific aim to understand the physical mechanisms of
85 ENSO better, and to improve its prediction (McPhaden and Yu 1999). As a result,
86 forecasts from dynamical models have significantly improved since 1985. However,
87 the majority of the operational statistical models do not utilize the more detailed
88 subsurface information provided by the observation system, which could effectively
89 help improve predictions further (Barnston et al. 2012). A novel dynamic components
90 statistical ENSO model (EDCM) was developed and described by Petrova et al. 2017
91 and 2020 which, along with surface zonal wind stress and temperature, specifically
92 samples subsurface temperature information from the western and central equatorial
93 Pacific Ocean (WPAC and CPAC) to predict ENSO events at lead times beyond one
94 year in advance. The EDCM has successfully hindcasted all major El Niños (EN)
95 since 1970 at leads of up to about 2 years in advance (Petrova et al. 2020),
96 demonstrating that such predictive lead times are possible also for statistical models.
97 Moreover, the last few EN, i.e. the 2014-2016, and the 2018-2020 events were
98 predicted in operational forecasting mode (see Petrova et al. 2017, Lowe et al. 2017,
99 Petrova et al. 2020, Petrova et al. 2021). These long-lead EN forecasts were used
100 within a dengue fever incidence model for the city of Machala in Ecuador, to assess
101 the probability of a dengue outbreak up to 11 months in advance (Lowe et al. 2017,
102 Petrova et al. 2021). In this way, EDCM was not only tested in real-time, but its
103 potential to extend the forecast lead time of a climate-sensitive disease was also
104 demonstrated.

105 When the first ENSO forecasts became a reality in the second half of the 1980s, it
106 also became obvious that such predictions could facilitate the generation of seasonal
107 climate forecasts, as well as their application for practical uses (Buizer et al. 2009).
108 ENSO associated droughts and flooding worldwide could be predicted some months
109 in advance, and the hope was that these predictions could help, for example,
110 vulnerable farming communities to prepare and plant more resilient crops, and
111 governments to save precious resources when planning for response to natural

112 hazards. Nowadays, many institutions around the globe (including IRI) tailor and
113 provide climate information and decision support systems on seasonal and interannual
114 time scales to the agricultural, health, energy, insurance, disaster reduction and other
115 sectors of society impacted by climate variability and change. However, despite the
116 immense practical utility of ENSO forecasts, attempts to issue predictions at longer
117 lead times, beyond the traditional 6 months in advance, have only been restricted to
118 the scientific undertaking, and none are issued on an operational level yet.

119

120 In the present study we use EDCM to perform in real-time statistical predictions of
121 the temperatures in the eastern equatorial Pacific for the winter of 2023/24 at
122 increasing lead times of up to 19 months in advance, and we investigate the potential
123 of such longer lead forecasts in assisting the climate impact community, decision-
124 makers around the world, and ultimately society, in alleviating the negative impacts of
125 ENSO. We describe the predictors and the dynamic components of the model in
126 Section 2. We summarize the ENSO forecasts in Section 3, and discuss the results and
127 implications of these longer leads for climate impacts and services in Section 4.

128

129 **2. Methods**

130 Here we apply EDCM, the statistical ENSO time series prediction model, based on
131 dynamic unobserved components derived from the decomposition of the Niño3.4
132 temperature time series, and described in detail in Petrova et al. 2017 and 2020, to
133 predict the monthly temperature in the Niño3.4 region ($[5^{\circ}\text{N} - 5^{\circ}\text{S}] \times [170^{\circ} - 120^{\circ}\text{W}]$)
134 for the 2023/24 boreal winter season. The model includes a trend component, a
135 seasonal component, and three cyclical components with different frequencies and
136 variances, as well as a number of regression (predictor) variables, and a noise term.
137 Given that the model includes a trend component, a detrending of the Niño3.4
138 temperature and predictor time series is not necessary. The trend, seasonal, and cycle
139 components are represented as linear dynamic stochastic processes driven by
140 disturbances (Harvey and Koopman 2000, Durbin and Koopman 2012). The cycle
141 components are estimated with periods corresponding to near-annual (NA), quasi-
142 biannual (QB) and quasi-quadrennial (QQ) frequencies, which are typical modes of
143 ENSO variability discussed at length in the literature (see Petrova et al. 2017 and

144 2020 and the references therein). The signal extraction of the different components,
145 the likelihood evaluation, and the actual ENSO forecasting are achieved by means of
146 the Kalman Filter (Kalman 1960). The statistical estimations and forecast method are
147 implemented and carried out by the software packages STAMP and OxMetrics
148 (Koopman et al. 2008 and 2010, Doornik 2013).

149 Predictions are initiated at particular lead times with respect to December 2023 (as it
150 is generally assumed that ENSO events peak around December). We look at
151 predictive lead times beyond boreal spring, in order to test the skill of the model to
152 overcome the well-known ENSO spring “predictability barrier” (Torrence and
153 Webster 1998, Sarachik and Cane 2010). Therefore, forecasts are initiated between 11
154 and 19 months ahead of a presumed December 2023 ENSO peak, i.e. between the
155 months of May 2022 and January 2023. As discussed in detail in Petrova et al. 2017,
156 EDCM makes use of different predictors at different lead times, ranging from
157 subsurface temperature at different depth levels, sea surface temperatures (SST), as
158 well as zonal wind stress (Supplementary Tables S1 and S2). These predictor indices
159 (their time series) are based on the general progression of a typical El Niño event
160 (EN), and are extracted from predefined regions in the western and central equatorial
161 Pacific (WPAC and CPAC; Petrova et al. 2017). Intensification of the trade winds and
162 a subsurface heat buildup in the WPAC, and its slow subsurface migration towards the
163 CPAC, along with westerly wind bursts at a later stage, are well-known to play a key
164 role in the onset of El Niño events (Wyrtki 1985; Cane et al. 1986; Jin 1997; Clarke
165 and Van Gorder 2003; McPhaden 2003, 2004; McPhaden et al. 2006; Ramesh and
166 Murtugudde 2013; Ballester et al. 2015 and 2016a; Petrova et al. 2017). In this regard,
167 EDCM benefits from available subsurface data to represent in detail these dynamical
168 processes and their interactions. In addition to these predictor variables, we also use a
169 previously identified SST dipole pattern in the extratropical South Pacific called the
170 RossBell dipole (RB SST) as an ENSO predictor at a lead time of 11 months (i.e. for
171 the forecast started in January 2023). The dipole was first defined in Ballester et al.
172 2011, and it represents a difference in SST warm and cold anomalies preceding EN
173 events near the Ross and Bellingshousen Seas, respectively (over the boxes $[65^{\circ} -$
174 $50^{\circ}\text{S}] \times [180^{\circ} - 160^{\circ}\text{W}]$ and $[65^{\circ} - 50^{\circ}\text{S}] \times [100^{\circ} - 80^{\circ}\text{W}]$). Its potential as an ENSO
175 predictor at a lead time of between 7-11 months has been discussed therein and in
176 Petrova et al. 2024. In particular RB peaks are followed by EN events approximately

177 9 months later. On the other hand, RB is anticipated by warming in the western
178 equatorial Pacific about an year in advance. Namely, the western equatorial surface
179 warming triggers an intensification of the local convection and upper tropospheric
180 divergence, generating an eastward and poleward propagating atmospheric wavetrain
181 in the southern extratropics (Ballester et al. 2011, Cvijanovic et al. 2017). This
182 wavetrain triggers the local SST anomalies that form the RB dipole in the south
183 Pacific. RB has also been used to predict other EN events within EDCM such as the
184 2009/10 and the 2015/16 EN (not shown).

185 For SST data we used the NOAA OISST V2 (Reynolds et al. 2002;
186 http://www.emc.ncep.noaa.gov/research/cmb/sst_analysis/); for subsurface
187 temperature data the Hadley Centre EN4.2.2 analyses data with the .g10 bias
188 correction (Good et al. 2013, Gouretski and Reseghetti 2010, Gouretski and Cheng
189 2020); and for the calculation of zonal wind stress we used the NCEP-NCAR
190 reanalysis wind data (Kalnay et al. 1996).

191

192

193 **3. Results**

194 *a. Climate conditions in the tropical Pacific in 2022 and the beginning of* 195 *2023*

196 Figure 1a shows the average SST anomalies for the months between July and October
197 2022. Visible are the cold La Niña-related anomalies in the EPAC and CPAC, as well
198 as a prominent warm anomaly in the North Pacific. Of interest here is the less intense,
199 but significant warm anomaly (Supplementary Fig. 1a shows the standardized SST
200 anomalies) in the far WPAC, extending south of the equator (selected by the red box).
201 It has been shown previously that warm SST anomalies in this area typically precede
202 El Niño events on average about 14-18 months in advance (Ballester et al. 2011 and
203 2016a, Petrova et al. 2017). The region highlighted in the red box in Figure 1a is the
204 region from which we extract SSTs to use as a predictor in EDCM. We highlight that
205 the grid-point maximum warm anomaly inside the box reaches $\sim 2^{\circ}\text{C}$, and is located
206 just to the south of the equator. The time series of this predictor index is shown in
207 Figure 1c. Since the index represents an average temperature value over the whole

208 box, it indicates a lower value than 2°C. The blue arrows highlight the warm anomaly
209 peaks that preceded past EN events, and a peak is also highlighted in July-October of
210 2022.

211

212

213

214

215

216

217

218

219

220

221

222

223

224

225

227 **Fig. 1: Surface oceanic conditions in 2022 and the beginning of 2023 conducive to El**
 228 **Niño, and SST time series of the predictors used in the EDCM model at lead times of**
 229 **15 and 11 months.** a) and b) Sea surface temperature (SST) anomalies [°C], c) SST
 230 anomalies extracted from the box [10°S-0°]x[140°-160°E], d) RossBell SST index. Red and
 231 black boxes in panels a-b include regions from which SST predictors have been extracted for

232 EDCM at different lead times with respect to the winter 2023/24 peak season. Arrows in
233 panels c-d indicate the time when a predictor is used for forecasting. “EN” labels indicate the
234 time of peak El Niño conditions. Linear trend lines are included for the time series in panels
235 c) and d) as grey solid lines. The period used to calculate a climatology is 1982-2022.

236

237

238

239

240

241

242

243

244

245

246

247

248

249

250

251

252

253

254

255

a) Zonal Wind Stress MAY-SEP 2022

b) Zonal Wind Stress MAR 2023

c) Wind Stress 15 MONTHS LEAD

d) Wind Stress 11 MONTHS LEAD

257

258

259 **Fig. 2: Surface atmospheric conditions in 2022 and the beginning of 2023**
260 **conducive to El Niño, and zonal wind stress time series of the predictors used in**
261 **the EDCM model at lead times of 15 and 11 months.** a) and b) Standardized zonal
262 wind stress anomalies [standard deviation], c) zonal wind stress [N/m^2] extracted from the
263 box [0° - $10^\circ N$] \times [160° - $200^\circ E$], d) zonal wind stress [N/m^2] extracted from the box [$10^\circ S$ -
264 0°] \times [180° - $210^\circ E$]. Red boxes in panels a-b include regions from which zonal wind stress
265 predictors have been extracted for EDCM at different lead times with respect to the winter
266 2023/24 peak season. Arrows in panels c-d indicate the time when a predictor is used for
267 forecasting. “EN” labels indicate the time of peak El Niño conditions. Linear trend lines are
268 included for the time series in panels c) and d) as grey solid lines. The period used to
269 calculate a climatology is 1982-2022.

270

271

272 Similarly, Figure 1b shows the SST anomalies in January 2023, and the RB dipole
273 feature in the South Pacific is captured by the red and black boxes. The boxes do not
274 encompass the areas of the strongest warm and cold anomalies, but we note that these
275 anomalies generally progress eastwards with the evolution of EN, and peak in the two
276 boxed regions about 7-9 months before the ENSO peak (i.e. in the months of March-
277 May; Ballester et al. 2011). At the time of writing, the data is only available until
278 January 2023, but it can be inferred from Figure 1b (Supplementary Fig. 1b) that the
279 anomalies may be better captured by our boxes in the months of March-May 2023, as
280 a result of the general eastward propagation of these features (Ballester et al. 2011).
281 The RB dipole time series is shown in Figure 1c and a prominent peak is also
282 highlighted at the very end of the time series in January 2022.

283 Standardized zonal wind stress anomalies in 2022 and the beginning of 2023 are
284 depicted in Figure 2, panels a and b. Panel a shows that strong easterly wind
285 anomalies occurred in the period between May and September of 2022, peaking in the
286 far WPAC region, as well as south of the equator towards the CPAC and EPAC.
287 Strong easterly wind anomalies at these locations precede EN events on average by
288 about 15-20 months in advance. Although our red box does not include the entire area
289 of strong trade wind anomalies, it does capture a significant portion of it. The zonal
290 wind stress time series extracted from the box-marked region is shown in Figure 2c. A
291 large trough indicative of easterly wind bursts is highlighted in the autumn months of

12

292 2022, also signaling the potential for a forthcoming EN event. We note that the
293 biggest troughs in Figure 2c are not always associated with EN events. The EDCM
294 predictive framework includes other statistical criteria to pinpoint the lead time at
295 which a given predictor is the most significant. In January of 2023 (Figure 2b) the
296 extended warm SST anomalies in the WPAC region generated some westerly wind
297 anomalies in the south, but also in the north off-equatorial regions in the CPAC,
298 features that are typical about 7-11 months prior to EN events (Eisenman et al. 2005).
299 The red box in Figure 2b captures some of these westerly wind burst anomalies. The
300 time series of the predictor extracted from this box is shown in Figure 2d, and a peak
301 associated with westerly wind bursts at the end of the time series in December-
302 January 2022/23 is highlighted.

303 Figure 3 depicts the subsurface temperature anomalies at different depths and in
304 different months between May and October 2022, along with boxes from which
305 predictors for EDCM were extracted. Strong warm anomalies in the WPAC are
306 observed between 150-300 meters depth in May, July and September of 2022, which
307 gradually progress eastward and are already stronger in the CPAC subsurface in
308 October 2022 (Figure 3g). The subsurface temperature time series predictors extracted
309 from the black boxes in Figure 3a and g are shown in Figure 3b and d, and the
310 predictors used at 12 and 13 months leads are also shown in Figure 3f and h. As seen
311 in all panels b, d, f and h of Figure 3, prominent and sustained positive peaks occur in
312 all the time series of subsurface temperature anomalies from the spring to the winter
313 months of 2022. Such strong subsurface warm anomalies always precede EN events
314 by on average 10-20 months (McPhaden 2004, Ramesh and Murtugudde 2013,
315 Petrova et al. 2017). Thus, climate conditions broadly spanning the spring, summer,
316 autumn and winter months of 2022/23 are collectively prime for a forthcoming EN
317 event in the winter of 2023/24.

318

319

320

321

Subsurface Temperature Predictors

a) 19 MONTHS LEAD/MAY 2022 (150m. DEPTH)

b) 150mR1 19 MONTHS LEAD

c) 17 MONTHS LEAD/JUL 2022 (300m. DEPTH)

d) 150mR2 14 MONTHS LEAD

e) 15 MONTHS LEAD/SEPT 2022 (250m. DEPTH)

f) 250mR2 13 MONTHS LEAD

g) 14 MONTHS LEAD/OCT 2022 (150m. DEPTH)

h) 250mR1 12 MONTHS LEAD

323

324

325 **Fig. 3: Subsurface oceanic conditions in 2022 conducive to El Niño, and subsurface**
326 **temperature time series of the predictors used in the EDCM model at different**
327 **lead times.** a) Temperature anomalies at 150 meters depth in May 2022, b) time series of
328 subsurface temperature at 150 meters depth extracted from the box [10°S-5°N]x[120°-
329 140°E], c) temperature anomalies at 300 meters depth in July 2022, d) time series of
330 subsurface temperature at 150 meters depth extracted from the box [7°S-7°N]x[150°-180°E],
331 e) temperature anomalies at 250 meters depth in September 2022, f) time series of subsurface
332 temperature at 250 meters depth extracted from the box [7°S-7°N]x[140°-170°E], g)
333 temperature anomalies at 150 meters depth in October 2022., h) time series of subsurface
334 temperature at 250 meters depth extracted from the box [7°S-7°N]x[120°-140°E]. Black
335 boxes in panels a, c, e and g indicate regions from which predictor time series for the model
336 were extracted. Arrows in panels b, d, f and h indicate the time when a predictor is used for
337 forecasting. “EN” labels indicate the time of peak El Niño conditions. Linear trend lines are
338 included for the time series in panels b), d), f) and h) as solid grey lines.

339

340

341 *b. ENSO forecasts for 2023/24*

342 Figure 4 shows forecasts of SST anomalies in the Niño3.4 region initiated in January
343 2023 (Figure 4a), September-December 2022 (Figure 4b-e), and July 2022 (Figure
344 4f), corresponding to leads from 11 to 17 months along with updated observations
345 (black solid line) until June 2024. The observed Niño3.4 values point to a moderate-
346 to-strong EN that peaks in December 2023. All forecasts in Figure 4 predict an EN to
347 mature in the winter of 2023/24 (Supplementary Table 3). Forecasts initiated at lead
348 times between 11-14 months foresee a moderate warm event, but a larger EN of
349 about 2°C amplitude is within the 70% confidence intervals of the predictions. The
350 actual observed peak was 1.99°C. The forecast closest to this amplitude is the one
351 issued 13 months in advance predicting a peak of 1.20°C (Supplementary Table 3).
352 Longer-lead forecasts initiated 15 to 19 months in advance (Figure 4e and f and
353 Supplementary Figure 2a) predict a weak EN for the winter of 2023/24. However,
354 forecasts initiated 22 and 24 months in advance of an assumed peak in December
355 2023 (i.e. in the months of February 2022 and December 2021) do not predict an EN
356 event, and show neutral conditions in the tropical Pacific instead (Supplementary

15

357 Figure 2b and c), suggesting we reached a limit of feasible lead times. It is well-
358 known especially for statistical ENSO models that the prediction of the amplitude of
359 an event is harder and less accurate with the increase of the lead time (Barnston et al.
360 2012, Petrova et al. 2017, 2020 and references therein). Hence, predictions started so
361 long in advance are likely to be incorrect, unless a very strong ENSO event is
362 developing in the tropical Pacific. For example, in Figure 9e of Petrova et al. 2017 it
363 can be seen that EDCM did not predict the weak 2014/15 EN at the very long lead
364 times of 22-24 months, as opposed to Figure 4 in Petrova et al. 2020, where all strong
365 EN events are successfully predicted even at the longer leads of 21 and 29 months in
366 advance, albeit with a smaller amplitude than observed. We also highlight that EDCM
367 makes use of different predictors at different lead times, and it could happen that a
368 given predictor affected the forecast more/less strongly, and this could directly impact
369 the amplitude of the predicted event. This could explain why EDCM predicted a
370 higher amplitude event at 13 months, as opposed to 11 or 12 months lead time. We
371 have seen a similar situation with the prediction of the 1997/98 EN for example (see
372 Figure 9a and 9f in Petrova et al. 2017, where the amplitude of the event is better
373 predicted at the very long lead times as opposed to the medium lead times).
374 Additionally, a deterioration of the forecast precision is observed when predictions are
375 initiated closer to the “spring predictability barrier” due to the general decrease of the
376 signal-to-noise ratio, hence, the lower amplitudes predicted at 11 and 12 months lead
377 time. However, the forecasted amplitudes at these leads are still greater than those
378 predicted beyond 13 months in advance. Finally, here we used the version of EDCM
379 that features a fixed seasonal cycle, which could explain the delay by a couple of
380 months in the predicted peaks at all lead times (see Petrova et al. 2017 for more
381 details on this issue).

382

383

384

385

386

387

388

389

390

391 **Fig. 4: Forecasts of the 2023/24 temperature anomalies [°C] in the Niño3.4 region.**
392 Forecast started in a) January 2023, b) December 2022, c) November 2022, d) October 2022,
393 e) September 2022, f) July 2022. In all panels the thick black line is the observations (shown
394 until June 2024), the red line is the forecast, the blue dash-and-dotted lines are the 70%
395 confidence intervals, and the black dotted lines are the -0.5°C and +0.5°C threshold for La
396 Niña and El Niño, respectively.

397

398

399 **4. Discussion and Conclusions**

400 ENSO is the principal driver of climate variability, and has the potential to trigger
401 weather- and climate-related natural and societal disasters worldwide. Climate
402 vulnerability and the socio-economic consequences in regions where ENSO
403 teleconnections are especially strong could be substantially reduced with the evolution
404 of ENSO forecasts, and society has a lot to gain if ENSO predictions can be extended
405 beyond the current operational limit of 6 months in advance. During the last several
406 years we have designed, tested and improved EDCM, an ENSO statistical forecasting
407 model (Petrova et al. 2017 and 2020), with the overarching goal to expand ENSO
408 statistical predictions to at least one year ahead of the mature phase, and test the
409 potential for even longer lead times. We were successful in hindcasting the major EN
410 events (the 1972/73, 1982/83, 1986/87, 1997/98, 2009/10 and 2015/16 ENs) 1.5 years
411 in advance, in some cases even 2.5 years ahead (Petrova et al. 2020). Here we
412 showcase our forecast for the winter of 2023/24, indicating that already in October of
413 2022 (14 months ahead of a presumed ENSO peak in December 2023) it was possible
414 to foresee a moderate to strong EN development in the tropical Pacific. Moreover, the
415 model predicts the return of EN even for forecasts initiated 17 and 19 months ahead
416 (i.e. in July and May of 2022, respectively), albeit the predicted amplitudes are for a
417 much weaker warm event (Figure 4f and Supplementary Figure 2a).

418 Climate conditions in the tropical Pacific in spring-winter of 2022 were also
419 compatible with the early onset and evolution of a warm event (Figures 1, 2 and 3), as
420 surface temperature, zonal wind stress and subsurface temperature anomalies are all
421 consistent with the EN preceding composite anomalies (see also Figures 6 and 7 of

422 Petrova et al. 2017). It is interesting to note that Figures 2c and d show a decreasing
423 trend in the zonal wind stress time series, corresponding to overall strengthening of
424 the easterly trade winds and the Walker Circulation in the last five years (from 2018-
425 2023). This recently observed trend change and strengthening of the zonal
426 atmospheric circulation in the tropical Pacific, along with an enhanced warming in the
427 WPAC region (also seen in all the time series extracted from the subsurface ocean in
428 the WPAC in Figure 3b, d, f and h) are generally in conflict with the CMIP5 and
429 CMIP6 climate projections for a unified warming in the equatorial Pacific, and a
430 weakening of the Walker cell (DiNezio et al. 2013, Kociuba et al. 2015). The
431 strengthening of the Walker circulation in recent observations has also been linked by
432 Heede and Fedorov 2021 and 2023 to global warming as opposed to natural climate
433 variability proposed by earlier studies (McGregor et al. 2018, Watanabe et al. 2020).

434 The QB and QQ modes of ENSO variability, corresponding to some of the EDCM
435 dynamic cyclical components (along with a near annual component), are also in their
436 growing phases in 2023 (Figure 5), signaling the high probability for an EN to occur.
437 In Figure 5 we have extended idealized versions of these oscillatory modes, along
438 with a decadal cycle corresponding to decadal ENSO variability (Petrova et al. 2020).
439 These cyclical components are time-varying in the model, and their frequency and
440 amplitude parameters can shift with changes in the overall climatic conditions, and as
441 a result of atmospheric noise. However, we can see that in the 2023/24 winter season
442 the idealized versions of the 2-year (QB), 4-year and 5-year cycles (QQ) are all in
443 their peak phases. In fact, a similar superposition of these cycles occurred in 1997/98,
444 when one of the biggest EN on record developed, despite the fact that the decadal
445 cycle was at its trough, as it is also in 2023.

446

447

448

449

450

451

452

454

455 **Fig. 5: Schematic of idealized oscillatory models involved in ENSO variability.** Shown
 456 are cycles of periodicities corresponding to a) 2 (dashed green) and 4 (solid beige) years, b)
 457 (dashed magenta) and 12 (solid black) years. Peak months of El Niño (pink lines) and La
 458 Niña (light blue lines) from the observations are indicated. The dark pink dash-dotted line
 459 indicates the forecasted El Niño at the end of 2023. Wave amplitudes are not realistic.

460

461

462 For the 2023/24 winter season, our long-term predictions of 11 to 14 months in
 463 advance all suggest moderate-to-strong EN developing in the Pacific. This is a
 464 substantially longer lead time than currently used in operational forecasts. For longer

20

465 15 to 19 months lead-times, our forecasts still suggest EN development in 2023/24,
466 albeit of weaker amplitude (Fig. 4 and Supplementary Fig. 2). Beyond these lead
467 times, predictions initiated 22 and 24 months in advance suggested neutral conditions
468 instead of an EN, despite the CI indicated that moderate EN conditions were possible
469 (Supplementary Fig. 2). These results illustrate strong potential for expanding the
470 statistical operational ENSO forecasts to 12 and 18 months in advance. Despite the
471 fact that longer 22 and 24 months forecasts were not feasible at this instance, our
472 success in predicting some of the previous ENSO events 2-2.5 years in advance (i.e.
473 the 1997/98, 2002/03, 2009/10, 2015/16 ENs, See Petrova et al. 2017 and 2020),
474 suggests that early ENSO forecasting is an avenue worth exploring further.

475 ENSO predictions are still constrained by the lack of complete physical
476 understanding, parametrization of key dynamical processes, and by initialization
477 errors due to imperfect data assimilation in the case of dynamical models, as well as
478 by the lack of long atmospheric and oceanic historical data in the case of statistical
479 models, in addition to the uncertainties arising from atmospheric noise (including the
480 so-called spring barrier), and natural climate variability (Wittenberg 2009, Barnston et
481 al. 2012, Fedorov et al. 2015). Nonetheless, this study adds to previous ones (Chen et
482 al. 2004; Luo et al. 2008; Izumo et al. 2010; Ludescher et al. 2013, 2014; Petrova et
483 al. 2017; Gonzalez and Goddard 2016; Ramesh et al. 2017; Luo et al. 2017; Meng et
484 al. 2020, Petrova et al. 2020) in voicing the potential of early ENSO predictions, and
485 call for a reconsideration and an increase of the official lead time at which operational
486 ENSO forecasting is performed.

487 Clearly, the information provided by longer lead forecasts is more specific, associated
488 with more uncertainty, and hence, suited to more specialized applications. In other
489 words, the longer lead forecasts indicate what is more likely to happen, but are far
490 from precise. For this reason, it is useful to explore the potential requirements of
491 decision makers, and tailor the information provided by longer lead ENSO forecasts
492 to those needs. For example, in health impact assessment infectious disease
493 predictions at longer lead times based on ENSO information for diseases such as
494 dengue and malaria could serve for saving resources and for devising optimized
495 intervention plans to control vector infestations, and help reduce mosquito breeding
496 sites, ultimately lowering the burden of disease and saving lives. In the area of energy
497 production, ENSO has considerable impact on hydropower, wind power and biomass

498 production, especially in the more affected areas in the Northwest US, South America,
499 Central America, the Iberian Peninsula, Southeast Asia and Southeast Australia (Ng et
500 al. 2017). The large share of hydropower electricity supply in some of these locations
501 means that an ENSO resilient renewable energy supply will become increasingly
502 important, and the sector would greatly benefit from long-term ENSO forecasting for
503 a mid-term adjustment of the energy mix. Some of these systems could be adapted to
504 apply such longer lead climate information in a probabilistic framework, so that
505 resources could indeed be optimized, and risks properly estimated on a tailored cost-
506 benefit basis, especially in less affluent countries and more vulnerable populations. In
507 others the added value of knowledge so long in advance could be limited for
508 mitigating risks related to climate variability and extremes. Therefore, such
509 predictions should be promoted to relevant sectors in a sustainable and targeted way.

510 Given these considerations, it is vital to establish an operational structural framework
511 for the issuing of such longer lead ENSO forecasts that is also based on local needs
512 and demands. This role could be taken again by the IRI/CPC, and an additional
513 forecasting plume could be released on a regular basis, including only models tailored
514 for longer lead forecasts, along with a consensus ENSO outlook at a lead time of at
515 least 1 year ahead.

516 In conclusion, we want to stress that ENSO forecasting has advanced to a point when
517 useful and reliable annual timescale forecasts can be made regularly. Our results here
518 indicated early on (already in July 2022) that an EN event was expected to mature in
519 the winter of 2023/24. The event was predicted to be most likely moderate or strong,
520 but in both cases the expected deviation in the global mean surface temperature as a
521 result of the release of heat from the equatorial Pacific Ocean to the atmosphere is
522 expected to be on the order of about 0.1°C or more (Christy and McNider 1994,
523 Wigley 2000). Therefore, 2024 could become the next warmest year on record, and
524 there is some likelihood that the mean increase of 1.5°C with respect to pre-industrial
525 temperature levels set as a threshold in the Paris Climate Agreement (Christoff 2016)
526 could be temporarily breached in the next year, should a stronger El Niño mature in
527 the eastern tropical Pacific.

528

529

530 *Acknowledgments.*

531 DP and IC were supported by La Caixa Junior Leader Grant 2020 (Marie
532 Sklodowska-Curie grant agreement No 847648). XR acknowledges support from
533 TipESM “Exploring Tipping Points and Their Impacts Using Earth System Models “,
534 funded by the European Union. Grant Agreement number. 101137673 DOI:
535 10.3030/101137673. Contribution Nr. 1. We acknowledge support from the
536 grant CEX2023-0001290-S funded by MCIN/AEI/ 10.13039/501100011033,
537 and support from the Generalitat de Catalunya through the CERCA Program.

538

539 *Data Availability Statement.*

540 The predictors (time series) for the ENSO model, as well as the Niño3.4 index used
541 here, represent data that were a reanalysis of existing data, which are openly available
542 at locations cited in the reference section. The modelling, estimation and forecasting
543 have been carried out by the software OxMetrics/STAMP and can be downloaded
544 from <https://www.doornik.com/>. A related software package is Time Series Lab and
545 can be found at <https://timeserieslab.com/>.

546

547

548

549

550

551

552

553

554

555

556

557

558

559

REFERENCES

560

Astudillo, H. F., R. Abarca-del-Río, and F.A. Borotto, 2017: Long-term potential nonlinear predictability of El Niño–La Niña events. *Climate Dynamics*, 49, pp.131-141.

563

Ballester, J., S. Bordoni, D. Petrova, and X. Rodó, 2015: On the dynamical mechanisms explaining the western Pacific subsurface temperature buildup leading to ENSO events. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 42(8), pp.2961-2967.

566

Ballester, J., M.À. Rodríguez-Arias, and X. Rodó, 2011: A new extratropical tracer describing the role of the western Pacific in the onset of El Niño: Implications for ENSO understanding and forecasting. *Journal of Climate*, 24(5), pp.1425-1437.

569

Ballester, J., S. Bordoni, D. Petrova, and X. Rodó, 2016: Heat advection processes leading to El Niño events as depicted by an ensemble of ocean assimilation products. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 121(6), pp.3710-3729.

572

Barnston, A. G., M. K. Tippett, M.L. L'Heureux, S. Li, and D. G. DeWitt, 2012: Skill of real-time seasonal ENSO model predictions during 2002–11: Is our capability increasing?. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 93(5), pp.631-651.

575

Buizer, J., K. Jacobs, and D. Cash, 2016: Making short-term climate forecasts useful: Linking science and action. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 113(17), pp.4597-4602.

578

Cane, M. A., S. E. Zebiak, and S. C. Dolan, 1986: Experimental forecasts of EL Nino. *Nature*, 321(6073), pp.827-832.

580

Chen, D., M. A. Cane, A. Kaplan, S. E. Zebiak, and D. Huang, 2004: Predictability of El Niño over the past 148 years. *Nature*, 428(6984), pp.733-736.

582

Chen, D. and Cane, M. A., 2008: El Niño prediction and predictability. *Journal of Computational Physics*, 227(7), pp.3625-3640.

584

Christy, J.R., and McNider, R.T., 1994: Satellite greenhouse signal, *Nature*, 367, pp.325.

585

586 Clarke, A.J. and Van Gorder, S., 2003: Improving El Niño prediction using a space-
587 time integration of Indo-Pacific winds and equatorial Pacific upper ocean heat
588 content. *Geophysical research letters*, 30(7).

589 Christoff, P., 2016: The promissory note: COP 21 and the Paris Climate Agreement.
590 *Environmental Politics*, 25(5), pp.765-787.

591 Cvijanovic, I., Santer, B.D., Bonfils, C. et al.,2017. Future loss of Arctic sea-ice cover
592 could drive a substantial decrease in California’s rainfall. *Nature Communications*, 8,
593 pp.1947.

594 DiNezio, P.N., Vecchi, G.A. and Clement, A.C., 2013. Detectability of changes in the
595 Walker circulation in response to global warming. *Journal of Climate*, 26(12),
596 pp.4038-4048.

597 DiNezio, P. N., C. Deser, Y. Okumura, and A. Karspeck,, 2017: Predictability of 2-
598 year La Niña events in a coupled general circulation model. *Climate dynamics*, 49,
599 pp.4237-4261.

600 Doornik, J. A. 2013: Object-Oriented Matrix Programming using Ox 7.0. Timberlake
601 Consultants Ltd, London. <http://www.doornik.com/>

602 Durbin, J. and Koopman, S.J., 2012: *Time series analysis by state space methods* (Vol.
603 38). OUP Oxford.

604 Eisenman, I, Yu, L., Tziperman, E., 2005: Westerly wind bursts: ENSO’s tail rather
605 than the dog? *Journal of Climate*, 18, pp. 5224-5238.

606 Fedorov, A. V., S. Hu, M. Lengaigne, and E. Guilyardi, 2015: The impact of westerly
607 wind bursts and ocean initial state on the development, and diversity of El Niño
608 events. *Climate Dynamics*, 44, pp.1381-1401.

609 Good, S. A., M. J. Martin, and N. A. Rayner, 2013: EN4: Quality controlled ocean
610 temperature and salinity profiles and monthly objective analyses with uncertainty
611 estimates. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 118(12), pp.6704-6716.

612 Gonzalez, P. L. and Goddard, L., 2016: Long-lead ENSO predictability from CMIP5
613 decadal hindcasts. *Climate Dynamics*, 46, pp.3127-3147.

614 Goswami, B. N. and Shukla, J., 1991: Predictability of a coupled ocean-atmosphere
615 model. *Journal of Climate*, 4(1), pp.3-22.

616 Gouretski, V. and Reseghetti, F., 2010: On depth and temperature biases in
617 bathythermograph data: Development of a new correction scheme based on analysis
618 of a global ocean database. *Deep Sea Research Part I: Oceanographic Research*
619 *Papers*, 57(6), pp.812-833.

620 Gouretski, V. and Cheng, L., 2020: Correction for systematic errors in the global
621 dataset of temperature profiles from mechanical bathythermographs. *Journal of*
622 *Atmospheric and Oceanic Technology*, 37(5), pp.841-855.

623 Harvey, A. and Koopman, S. J., 2000: Signal extraction and the formulation of
624 unobserved components models. *The Econometrics Journal*, 3(1), pp.84-107.

625 Heede, U. K. and Fedorov, A. V., 2021: Eastern equatorial Pacific warming delayed
626 by aerosols and thermostat response to CO₂ increase. *Nature Climate Change*, 11(8),
627 pp.696-703.

628 Heede, U. K. and Fedorov, A. V., 2023: Colder eastern equatorial Pacific and stronger
629 Walker circulation in the early 21st century: separating the forced response to global
630 warming from natural variability. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 50(3),
631 p.e2022GL101020.

632 Izumo, T., J. Vialard, M. Lengaigne, C. de Boyer Montegut, S. K. Behera, J. J. Luo,
633 S. Cravatte, S. Masson, and T. Yamagata, 2010: Influence of the state of the Indian
634 Ocean Dipole on the following year's El Niño. *Nature Geoscience*, 3(3), pp.168-172.

635 Jin, F. F., 1997: An equatorial ocean recharge paradigm for ENSO. Part I: Conceptual
636 model. *Journal of the atmospheric sciences*, 54(7), pp.811-829.

637 Kalman, R. E., 1960: A new approach to linear filtering and prediction problems. *J.*
638 *Basic Eng.* March 1960; 82(1): 35–45

639 Kalnay, E., M. Kanamitsu, R. Kistler, W. Collins, D. Deaven, L. Gandin, M. Iredell,
640 Saha, S., G. White, J. Woollen, and Y. Zhu, 1996: The NCEP/NCAR 40-year
641 reanalysis project. *Bulletin of the American meteorological Society*, 77(3), pp.437-
642 472.

643 Kociuba, G. and Power, S. B., 2015: Inability of CMIP5 models to simulate recent
644 strengthening of the Walker circulation: Implications for projections. *Journal of*
645 *Climate*, 28(1), pp.20-35.

646 Koopman, S. J., N. Shephard, and J. A. Doornik, 2008: Statistical algorithms for
647 models in state space form: Ssfpack 3.0. Timberlake Consultants Press, London.

648 Koopman, S. J., A. C. Harvey, J. A. Doornik, and N. Shephard, 2010: Stamp 8.3:
649 Structural time series analyser, modeller and predictor. *London: Timberlake*
650 *Consultants*, 397.

651 Kumar, A., Z. Z. Hu, B. Jha, and P. Peng, 2017: Estimating ENSO predictability based
652 on multi-model hindcasts. *Climate Dynamics*, 48, pp.39-51.

653 Latif, M., D. Anderson, T. Barnett, M. Cane, R. Kleeman, A. Leetmaa, J. O'Brien, A.
654 Rosati, and E. Schneider, 1998: A review of the predictability and prediction of
655 ENSO. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 103(C7), pp.14375-14393.

656 L'Heureux, M. L., A. F. Levine, M. Newman, C. Ganter, J. J. Luo, M. K. Tippett, and
657 T. N. Stockdale, 2020: ENSO prediction. *El Niño Southern Oscillation in a changing*
658 *climate*, pp.227-246.

659 Lowe, R., A. M. Stewart-Ibarra, D. Petrova, M. García-Díez, M. J. Borbor-Cordova,
660 R. Mejía, M. Regato, and X. Rodó, 2017: Climate services for health: predicting the
661 evolution of the 2016 dengue season in Machala, Ecuador. *The lancet Planetary*
662 *health*, 1(4), pp.e142-e151.

663 Ludescher, J., A. Gozolchiani, M. I. Bogachev, A. Bunde, S. Havlin, and H. J.
664 Schellnhuber, 2013: Improved El Niño forecasting by cooperativity detection.
665 *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 110(29), pp.11742-11745.

666 Ludescher, J., A. Gozolchiani, M. I. Bogachev, A. Bunde, S. Havlin, and H. J.
667 Schellnhuber, 2014: Very early warning of next El Niño. *Proceedings of the National*
668 *Academy of Sciences*, 111(6), pp.2064-2066.

669 Luo, J. J., S. Masson, S. K. Behera, and T. Yamagata, 2008: Extended ENSO
670 predictions using a fully coupled ocean–atmosphere model. *Journal of Climate*, 21(1),
671 pp.84-93.

672 Luo, J. J., G. Liu, H. Hendon, O. Alves, and T. Yamagata, 2017: Inter-basin sources
673 for two-year predictability of the multi-year La Niña event in 2010–2012. *Scientific*
674 *reports*, 7(1), p.2276.

675 McGregor, S., M. F. Stuecker, J. B. Kajtar, M. H. England, and M. Collins, 2018:
676 Model tropical Atlantic biases underpin diminished Pacific decadal variability. *Nature*
677 *Climate Change*, 8(6), pp.493-498.

678 McPhaden, M. J. and Yu, X., 1999: Equatorial waves and the 1997–98 El Niño.
679 *Geophysical Research Letters*, 26(19), pp.2961-2964.

680 McPhaden, M. J., 2003: Tropical Pacific Ocean heat content variations and ENSO
681 persistence barriers. *Geophysical research letters*, 30(9).

682 McPhaden, M. J., 2004: Evolution of the 2002/03 El Niño. *Bulletin of the American*
683 *Meteorological Society*, 85(5), pp.677-696.

684 McPhaden, M. J., X. Zhang, H. H. Hendon, and M. C. Wheeler, 2006: Large scale
685 dynamics and MJO forcing of ENSO variability. *Geophysical research letters*, 33(16).

686 Meng, J., J., Fan, J. Ludescher, A. Agarwal, X. Chen, A. Bunde, J. Kurths, and H. J.
687 Schellnhuber, 2020: Complexity-based approach for El Niño magnitude forecasting
688 before the spring predictability barrier. *Proceedings of the National Academy of*
689 *Sciences*, 117(1), pp.177-183.

690 Ng, J. Y., S. W. Turner, and S. Galelli, 2017: Influence of El Niño Southern
691 Oscillation on global hydropower production. *Environmental Research Letters*, 12(3),
692 p.034010.

693 Petrova, D., S. J. Koopman, J. Ballester, and X. Rodó, 2017: Improving the long-lead
694 predictability of El Niño using a novel forecasting scheme based on a dynamic
695 components model. *Climate Dynamics*, 48, pp.1249-1276.

696 Petrova, D., J. Ballester, S. J. Koopman, and X. Rodó, 2020: Multiyear statistical
697 prediction of ENSO enhanced by the tropical Pacific observing system. *Journal of*
698 *Climate*, 33(1), pp.163-174.

699 Petrova, D., X. Rodó, R. Sippy, J. Ballester, R. Mejía, E. Beltrán-Ayala, M. J. Borbor-
700 Cordova, G. M. Vallejo, A. J. Olmedo, A. M. Stewart-Ibarra, and R. Lowe, 2021: The
701 2018–2019 weak El Niño: Predicting the risk of a dengue outbreak in Machala,
702 Ecuador. *International Journal of Climatology*, 41(7), pp.3813-3823.

703 Petrova, D., J. Ballester, and X. Rodó, 2024: RossBell Dipole and PSA mode
704 dynamics: combination forcing by ENSO and the annual cycle. Under revision in
705 *Journal of Climate*.

706 Philander, S. G. H., 1983: El Niño Southern Oscillation Phenomena. *Nature*,
707 302(5906), pp.295-301.

708 Ramesh, N., M. A. Cane, R. Seager, and D. E. Lee, 2017: Predictability and prediction
709 of persistent cool states of the Tropical Pacific Ocean. *Climate Dynamics*, 49,
710 pp.2291-2307.

711 Ramesh, N. and Murtugudde, R., 2013: All flavours of El Niño have similar early
712 subsurface origins. *Nature Climate Change*, 3(1), pp.42-46.

713 Reynolds, R. W., N. A. Rayner, T. M. Smith, D. C. Stokes, and W. Wang, 2002: An
714 improved in situ and satellite SST analysis for climate. *Journal of climate*, 15(13),
715 pp.1609-1625.

716 Rodó, X., M. A. Rodriguez-Arias, and J. Ballester, 2006: The role of ENSO in
717 fostering teleconnection patterns between the tropical north Atlantic and the western
718 Mediterranean basin. *CLIVAR Exchanges*, 11, pp.26-27.

719 Ropelewski, C. F. and Halpert, M. S., 1987: Global and regional scale precipitation
720 patterns associated with the El Niño/Southern Oscillation. *Monthly weather review*,
721 115(8), pp.1606-1626.

722 Sarachik, E. S. and Cane, M. A., 2010: *The El Nino-southern oscillation phenomenon*.
723 Cambridge University Press.

724 Torrence, C. and Webster, P. J., 1998: The annual cycle of persistence in the El
725 Niño/Southern Oscillation. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*,
726 124(550), pp.1985-2004.

727 Watanabe, M., J. L. Dufresne, Y. Kosaka, T. Mauritsen, and H. Tatebe, 2021:
728 Enhanced warming constrained by past trends in equatorial Pacific sea surface
729 temperature gradient. *Nature Climate Change*, 11(1), pp.33-37.

730 Wigley, T.M.L., 2000: ENSO, volcanoes, and record-breaking temperatures,
731 *Geophysical Research Letters*, 27, pp. 4101-4104.

732 Wittenberg, A. T., A. Rosati, T. L. Delworth, G. A. Vecchi, and F. Zeng, 2014: ENSO
733 modulation: is it decadal predictability?. *Journal of Climate*, 27(7), pp.2667-2681.

734 Wyrski, K., 1975: El Niño - the dynamic response of the equatorial Pacific Ocean to
735 atmospheric forcing. *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, 5(4), pp.572-584.

736 Wyrтки, K., 1985: Water displacements in the Pacific and the genesis of El Niño
737 cycles. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, 90(C4), pp.7129-7132.